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ECO-FRIENDLY ENERGY GENERATOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces useful concept of the present day scenario, power is a major need for human life. There is a need to develop non- conventional sources for power generation due to the reason that our conventional sources of power are getting scarcer by the day. This paper emphasizes on the idea that the kinetic energy getting wasted while vehicles move can be utilized to generate power by using a special arrangement of Spring/Piston Assembly with Water Tank. This generated power can be used for general purpose applications like streetlights, traffic signals. In addition, we could also have solar panels, which would satisfy our power needs, when there is no vehicular movement.

KEY WORDS- Kinetic energy, Speed breaker, Electro-mechanical unit, Conventional Energy, Power generation, Energy conservation